

*Devyāmata*, chapter 76: the distribution [of deities] in the site (vāstu), translation.

[The 9 by 9 part site]

76.1 Then one should divide the carefully measured, square site (kṣetra). It should be divided into 9 in both directions (north-south and east-west), into a fine 81-part [figure].

76.2 The wise man should then arrange the site deities in the site (vāstu). Next hear where [the deities], Brahmā, etc., are stationed.

76.3 On the square site (kṣetra), divided into 9 at each side, in an 81-part [figure], lord Brahmā has 9 parts.

76.4 Āryamā, Vivasvant, Mitra and Pṛthivīdhara have 6 parts [each], next to Brahmā, from the east onward.

76.5 Savitṛ, Indra, Skanda and Āpavatsa border Brahmā, in the corners, in sequence, from the southeast onwards.

76.6 Sāvitrī, Jaya, Rudra and Āpa are stationed next to Brahmā, in due order.

76.7 The 13 site (vāstu) deities in the centre of the site have been described. The rest, Īśāna, etc., are positioned outside the centre of the site.

76.1-16b: For an illustration of the 9 by 9 part site as described here, see figure 5c.

76.8-11 These deities are: Īśa, Meghādhīpa (Parjanya), Jayanta, Mahendra, Āditya, Satya, Bhṛśa, and Ambara (Antarikṣa), Agni, Pūṣan, Vitatha, Gṛhakṣata, Yama, Gandharva, Bhṛṅga, Mṛga, the Pitṛs, Dvauvārika, Sugrīva, Puṣpadanta, Varuṇa, Asura, Śoṣa, Pāpayakṣman, Roga, Vāsuki, Mukhya, Bhalvāṭa, Soma, Ananta, Aditi, and Diti.

76.12 Going from Īśāna onward, these further 32 [deities] are taught. They should be ascertained with all effort, set around the edge, within the vāstu.

76.13-14 Jayanta, Bhṛśa, Vitatha, Bhṛṅga, Sugrīva, Śoṣa, Mukhya and Aditi, in turn: these 8 deities have 2 cells each. The other deities have 1 cell each.

76.11a rogaś: The correction from nāgaś is made with support elsewhere in DM, for example at 79.13a.

76.15 There are 4 others, Carakī, etc., to be understood, stationed outside [the site]. They are at the corners, from the northeast onward, without a cell assignment.

76.16ab The 81-cell site (vāstu) has been particularly described.

[The 8 by 8 part site]

76.16cd Now, my dear, hear about the 64-cell one.

76.17 On a square site (kṣetra), divided into 8 in both directions (north-south and east-west), with diagonal lines from the Brahmā position,

76.18 in the 64-cell [site], Brahmā is on 4 cells in the centre. The [other] site (vāstu) deities are positioned all around that.

76.19 Āryaman has two cells; Vivasvant has two cells too; Mitra has two cells; and Pṛthivīdhara has the same.

76.20-21 These deities on 2 cells adjoin Brahmā in the cardinal directions. There are pairs at each corner. The rest, Savitṛ, Sāvitrī, Indra, Jaya, Rājyakṣa, Rudra, Āpavatsa and Āpa, have ½ a cell each.

76.16c-24: For an illustration of the 8 by 8 part site as described here, see figure 4d.

76.20c dvau dvau koṇeṣu bodhavyāḥ: Antarikṣa and Agni are in the southeast, Mṛga and Pitṛ in the southwest; Pāpayakṣman and Roga in the northwest; and Diti and Īśa in the northeast.

76.22-23b Parjanya, Bhṛśa, Pūṣan, Bhṛṅga, Dvauvārika, Śoṣa, Nāga and Aditi have half plus a half of a part (that is, 1 part) each, to each side of the corners.

76.23cd The remaining 16 have 2 cells each, in due sequence.

76.24 The distribution of parts and the positions of Īśa, etc. have been taught. Similarly, one should set Carakī, etc., outside, at the corners.

76.25 The deities, Brahmā, etc., in the site (vāstu) area have been taught. Their mantra is their own name, framed in the dīpa and jāti.

76.26 The 2-fold site (vāstu), 81-cell and 64-cell, has been described. Next hear more particulars.

Chapter 76, the distribution [of deities] in the vāstu.

76.22c rogaś: As at 11a, the correction from nāgaś is made with support elsewhere in DM, for example at 79.13a.